

PRIME CONSTELLATIONS CONJECTURE PROOF

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ABSTRACT: In this article we give a proof of the prime constellations conjecture . Our proof is so rigorous in the sense that it is based on the correctness of the Chebotarev- Artin theorem. We have all along our approach introduced a class of very interesting prime which said to be k -admissible that prime . This class is interesting because it serves as a brick to generate prime constellations of length k . Our results predict that the distribution of its prime numbers is worth :

$$(1 - Y_{k,\infty}) \frac{n}{\ln n}$$

where

$$Y_{k,\infty} = k - \sum_{t=1}^k \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}, p \nmid a_t} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\beta_{\theta(p)} - 1} (p - 1)}\right)$$

1 INTRODUCTION

The prime k -tuple conjecture states that for any admissible set $\mathbb{A}_k = \{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$ of positive integers there are infinitely many integers n such that all $n + a_i$ are prime simultaneously. The set $\mathbb{A}_k = \{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$ is admissible if there is no trivial congruence obstruction. In other hand the set \mathbb{A}_k does not contain a complete set of residues modulo any prime $p \leq k$. The version of these conjecture has been formulated by Hardy and Littlewood and Later by Bateman and Horn . it starts that

$$\text{card}(n \leq n : n + a_i \in \mathbb{P}, \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}) \sim \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1 - \frac{\omega(p)}{p}}{(1 - \frac{1}{p})^k} \int_2^N \frac{du}{\ln^k(u)}$$

Where $\omega(p) = \text{card}(n \leq N : \prod_{i=1}^k (n + a_i) \equiv 0[p])$ The purpose of this paper, is to provide what we believe is a method which could lead to a complete solution For this problem.for clarity of our arguments we consider the a natural integer given arbitrarily large and then designate by C_n the set of the old composite integers of the interval $[9, n]$. Let f_n be the function defined as :

$$f_n : C_n \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^k$$

$$m \mapsto (m + a_1, m + a_2, \dots, m + a_k) \quad \text{Let}$$

$$G_i = \{m + a_i \in P_{n+a_i} : m \in C_n\}$$

Definition

1.1 k - f_n ADMISSIBLE PRIME

An integer m is called to be k - f_n admissible prime if $f_n(m)$ has at least one component prime .The set of k - f_n admissible prime $\bigcup_{i=1}^k G_i$

1.2 k ADMISSIBLE Thot Primes

A k admissible Thot prime is the prime $p \geq \max(a_1, \dots, a_k) + 5$ such that $p - a_i$ is prime $\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$.

2 LEMMAS

2.1 LEMMA 1

$\forall n \geq 20, P_{n+\max(a_1, \dots, a_k)} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k G_i \neq \emptyset$

2.2 LEMMA 2

$\forall n \geq 9$ the set of Thot primes contains

$$\{p \in P_{n+6} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k G_i : \max(a_1, \dots, a_k) + 5 \leq p \leq n + \min(a_1, \dots, a_k)\}$$

2.3 USEFULL LEMMA

Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r be r numbers Then

$$1 - \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{1}{a_i} + \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq r} \frac{1}{a_i a_j} + \dots + \frac{(-1)^r}{a_1 a_2 \dots a_r} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{a_i - 1}{a_i}$$

3 THEOREM

Let n, k the given integers and denote by $R(n, k)$ the function which counts the number of k - f_n admissible prime. Then

$$R(n, k) = Y_{k, \infty} \frac{n}{\ln n}$$

with

$$Y_{k, \infty} = k - \sum_{t=1}^k \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}, p \nmid a_t} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\beta_{\theta(p)} - 1} (p-1)}\right)$$

4 Prime constellation Conjecture

4.1 PROOF OF USEFULL LEMMA

For the proof of USEFULL LEMMA, we consider the Polynomial:

$$P(X) = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(X - \frac{1}{a_i}\right)$$

from the coefficient-roots relations we also have :

$$P(X) = X^r + \sum_{k=1}^r \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq r} \frac{(-1)^k X^{r-k}}{\prod_{j=1}^k a_{i_j}}$$

For $X = 1$ the result follows

4.2 PROOF OF THE THEOREM

Each $m \in C_n$ has at least one prime divisor $p \leq \sqrt{n}$

Let $r = \max\{i : p_i \leq \sqrt{n}\}$ $C_n = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}}, p \geq 3} A_{2p}$ with $A_{2p} = \{3p, 4p, 5p, \dots, [\frac{n-p}{2p}]p\}$

$$f_n(C_n) = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}}, p \geq 3} f_n(A_{2p})$$

Then $f_n(C_n) = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}}, p \geq 3} \prod_{i=1}^k \{A_{2p} + a_i\}$ Denote by ρ_k the function which counts the number of k - f_n admissible prime in a given set A then by the Poincare sieve we have:

$$\rho_k(f_n(C_n)) = \sum_{s=2}^r (-1)^s \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 < \dots < i_s \leq r} \rho_k\left(\bigcap_{j=2}^s f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}})\right)$$

Also

$$\forall s \geq 3, \bigcap_{j=2}^s f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}}) = \{(m \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j} + a_1, m \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j} + a_2, \dots, m \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j} + a_k) : 1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}} \rfloor\}$$

Let $E_{t,m} = \{m \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j} + a_t\}$ Counting the number of k - f_n admissible prime in $\bigcap_{j=2}^s f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}})$ consisting on counting the number of prime in $\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}} \rfloor} \bigcup_{t=1}^k E_{t,m}$

$$\rho_k(\bigcap_{j=2}^s f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}})) = \rho_k(\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}} \rfloor} \bigcup_{t=1}^k E_{t,m})$$

Then

$$\rho(\bigcup_{t=1}^k \bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{t,m}) = \rho(\bigcup_{t=1}^k Z_t)$$

Where

$$Z_t = \bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{t,m}$$

$$\rho(\bigcup_{t=1}^k Z_t) = \sum_{t=1}^k (-1)^{t-1} \sum_{1 \leq t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_t \leq t} \rho(\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j})$$

As $\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j} = \bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^s p_{i_j}} \rfloor} \bigcap_{j=1}^t E_{t_j,m}$ and

$$\bigcap_{j=1}^t E_{t_j,m} = X_{m,j}$$

With $X_{m,j} = \{m \prod_{2 \leq j_2 \leq j_3 \dots \leq j_s \leq s} \prod_{k=2}^s p_{i_{j_k}} + a_{t_j}\}$

Prime in $\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j}, \forall t$

Counting the number of prime in $\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j}$ corresponding to count the number of prime in arithmetic progression of reason $\prod_{2 \leq j_2 \leq j_3 \dots \leq j_s \leq s} \prod_{k=2}^s p_{i_{j_k}}$ By Chebotarev-Artin theorem we have

$$\rho(\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j}) = \sum_{j=1}^t \frac{\Pi(n + a_{t_j})}{\phi(\prod_{2 \leq j_2 \leq j_3 \dots \leq j_s \leq s} \prod_{k=2}^s p_{i_{j_k}}, p_{i_{j_k}} \nmid a_{t_j})} + g(n)$$

Let

$$E_2 = \{m \in \{2, 3, \dots, s\} : j_m = 2\}$$

and

$$E_k = \{m \notin E_{k-1} : j_m = k\}; \forall 3 \leq k \leq s$$

In obvious manner we have

$$\prod_{2 \leq j_2 \leq j_3 \dots \leq j_s \leq s} \left(\prod_{k=2}^s p_{i_{j_k}}, p_{i_{j_k}} \nmid a_{t_j} \right) = \prod_{m=2}^s (p_{i_m}^{\beta_m}, p_{i_m} \nmid a_{t_j})$$

where $\beta_m = \text{card}(E_m)$ Let

$$b(s) = \sum_{t=1}^k (-1)^{t-1} \sum_{1 \leq t_1 < t_2 \dots < t_t \leq t} \rho \left(\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j} \right)$$

Since $\phi \left(\prod_{j=2}^s (p_{i_j}^{\beta_j}, p_{i_j} \nmid a_{t_j}) \right) = \prod_{m=2}^s (p_{i_m}^{\beta_m-1} (p_{i_m-1}), p_{i_m} \nmid a_{t_j})$ Then

$$d(n) = \sum_{t=1}^k (-1)^{t-1} \sum_{1 \leq t_1 < t_2 \dots < t_t \leq t} \sum_{j=1}^t \frac{\Pi(n + a_{t_j})}{\prod_{m=2}^s (p_{i_m}^{\beta_m-1} (p_{i_m-1}), p_{i_m} \nmid a_{t_j})} + g(s)$$

With $d(n) = \sum_{t=1}^k (-1)^{t-1} \sum_{1 \leq t_1 < t_2 \dots < t_t \leq t} \rho \left(\bigcap_{j=1}^t Z_{t_j} \right)$ and also

$$f_n(A_{2p_i}) = d(2) - \sum_{j=1}^k \psi(p_i + a_j)$$

Then

$$d(n) = \sum_{t=1}^k \frac{\Pi(n + a_t)}{\prod_{m=2}^s (p_{i_m}^{\beta_m-1} (p_{i_m-1}), p_{i_m} \nmid a_t)} + g(s)$$

Let $r_{i_m} = p_{i_m}^{\beta_m-1} (p_{i_m-1})$ and $\sigma : \begin{matrix} \{2, 3, \dots, r\} & \rightarrow & \{2, 3, \dots, r\} \\ m & \mapsto & i_m \end{matrix}$

$$\rho_k(f_n(C_n)) = \sum_{s=2}^r (-1)^s \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_s \leq r} d(n) - \sum_{i=2}^r \sum_{j=1}^k \psi(p_i + a_j) + g(n)$$

Pulling

$$\omega(n) = \sum_{s=2}^r (-1)^s \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_s \leq r} d(n)$$

Then

$$\omega(n) = \sum_{s=2}^r (-1)^s \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_s \leq r} \sum_{t=1}^k \frac{\Pi(n + a_t)}{\prod_{m=2}^s (r_{i_m}, p_{i_m} \nmid a_t)}$$

By the usefull lemma we have :

$$\omega(n) = \sum_{t=1}^k \Pi(n + a_t) \left[1 - \prod_{i=2}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{r_i, p_i \nmid a_t} \right) \right]$$

Which

$$r_i = p_i^{\beta_{\sigma^{-1}(i)} - 1} (p_i - 1)$$

Hence

$$\rho_k(f_n(C_n)) = \sum_{t=1}^k \Pi(n + a_t) \left[1 - \prod_{i=2}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{\beta_{\sigma^{-1}(i)} - 1} (p_i - 1), p_i \nmid a_t} \right) \right] - \sum_{i=2}^r \sum_{j=1}^k \psi(p_i + a_j) + g(n)$$

Let

$$R_1(n) = \frac{\rho_k(f_n(C_n))}{Pi(n + \max(a_1, \dots, a_k))}$$

and

$$\theta(p_i) = \sigma^{-1}(i)$$

Then

$$R_1(n) \sim_{+\infty} Y_{k,\infty}$$

Where

$$Y_{k,\infty} = k - \sum_{t=1}^k \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}, p \nmid a_t} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\beta_{\theta(p)} - 1} (p - 1)} \right)$$

As

$$\rho_k(f_n(C_n)) = R_1(n) Pi(n + \max(a_1, \dots, a_k))$$

and

$$Pi(n + \max(a_1, \dots, a_k)) \sim_{+\infty} \frac{n}{\ln(n)}$$

Then

$$\rho_k(f_n(C_n)) \sim_{+\infty} Y_{k,\infty} \frac{n}{\ln n}$$

The Theorem is proved

4.3 PROOF OF LEMMA 1

From the fact that :

$$\text{card}(P_{n+\max(a_1, \dots, a_k)} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k G_i) + \rho_k(f_n(C_n)) = \Pi(n + \max(a_1, \dots, a_k))$$

We have

$$\text{card}(P_{n+\max(a_1, \dots, a_k)} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k G_i) \sim_{+\infty} (1 - Y_{k, \infty}) \frac{n}{\ln n}$$

Study of $Y_{k, \infty}$

As

$$1 - Y_{k, \infty} = 1 - \sum_{t=1}^k \left[1 - \prod_{p \in \mathbb{P}, p \nmid a_t} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{\beta_{\theta(p)} - 1} (p - 1)} \right) \right]$$

Then

$$Y_{k, \infty} < 1$$

and in obvious manner we have

$$Y_{k, \infty} > 0$$

By using the information about

$$Y_{k, \infty}$$

the lemma is thus proved

4.4 PROOF OF THE LEMMA 2

By the lemma we can consider $p \in P_{n+6} \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k G_i \forall n \geq 9$. if $\exists i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ such that $p - a_i \notin \mathbb{P}$ then $p - a_i$ would belong to C_n . As $f_n(p - a_i)$ has p as one of its components hence p would belong to G_i . this consequence does not hold then the lemma is true

References

- [1] Richard K. Guy, Unsolved problems in number theory, Third Edition, Springer-Verlag, Berlin (2004).
- [2] Lecture on NX(p) Jean pierre serre

- [3] Thomas R. Nicely, Prime constellations research project, electronic (18 August 2004), posted at <http://www.trnicely.net/counts.html>.
- [4] H. Riesel, Prime numbers and computer methods for factorization, Progress in Mathematics Vol, 126, Birkhäuser Boston, Boston, MA, 1994.
- [5] Chris Caldwell. The Prime Glossary: prime triple and prime quadruple
- [6] R.P. Brent, The distribution of small gaps between successive prime numbers, Math. Comp. 28 (1974), 315–324
- [7] P.A. Clement, Congruences for sets of primes, AMM 56 (1949), 23–25
- [8] P. Ribenboim, The new book of prime number records, Springer, 1996
- [9] H.L. Montgomery and R.C. Vaughan, On the distribution of reduced residues, Annals of Math., 2nd series 123 (1986), no. 2, 311–333.
- [10] J. Young and A. Potler, First occurrence of prime gaps, Math. Comp. 52 (1989), 221– 224.
- [11] G.H. Hardy and J.E. Littlewood, Some problems in 'partitio numerorum' iii: On the expression of a number as a sum of primes, G.H. Hardy Collected Papers, vol. 1, Clarendon Press, 1966, pp. 561–630.
- [12] B. Green and T. Tao, The primes contain arbitrarily long arithmetic progressions, arXiv, no. 0404188v6, (2007)